

Teachers' Leadership Practices, Professional Learning Commitment and Child Development

Ann Lorien P. Tacang

Abstract. The study unfolded the extent of teachers' leadership practices, professional learning commitment, and child development, which may be influenced by leadership and professional learning communities in Governor Generoso South District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. The study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing adapted survey instruments to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data collected were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of leadership practices and professional learning communities in terms of decision-making authority and collaboration was moderately extensive. At the same time, teachers' perception of child development was extensive. There was a significant correlation between leadership practices, professional learning communities, and perception of child development. Domains of leadership practices and professional learning communities in terms of instructional leadership, teacher support, collaboration, trust, communication, and decision-making authority significantly influenced development. Future research may explore the potential role of vision goal setting and professional development opportunities, considering the evolving nature of education.

KEY WORDS

1. teacher leadership practices
2. professional learning communities
3. child development

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1. Introduction

Educators worldwide are recognizing the significance of nurturing not only academic skills but also the social, emotional, physical, and moral dimensions of a child's growth. This shift reflects a growing body of research that underscores the lifelong benefits of a more comprehensive approach to early education. Another significant trend is the adoption of play-based learning as a primary pedagogical approach. Many countries are redefining the role of play in education, acknowledging its power to promote cognitive, social, and emotional development in young children. Kindergarten teachers are reevaluating their perceptions to see play as an integral part of the learning process, essential for building a strong educational foundation (Perkmen et.al., 2023). Cultural and regional variations continue to influence kindergarten teachers' perceptions of whole-child development. While there is a global trend towards holistic education, some cultures maintain a strong emphasis on academic achieve-

ment, while others prioritize character education, social skills, and overall well-being (Graham, 2022). In the context of Philippine education, leadership practices and professional learning communities play pivotal roles in influencing kindergarten teachers' perceptions of whole-child development. Leadership practices, when characterized by visionary and supportive leaders, can set the tone for a school's educational priorities. When school administrators emphasize a holistic approach to education, teachers are more likely to perceive whole-child development as central to their mission. Leaders who prioritize non-academic skills, social-emotional learning, and a well-rounded curriculum create an environment where teachers feel encouraged and empowered to adopt a similar perspective (Macam, 2022). Professional learning communities (PLCs) also have a significant impact on teacher perceptions in the Philippines. Within PLCs, educators engage in collaborative discussions, share best practices, and access professional development opportunities. When these communities foster a culture of reflective practice and the exchange of ideas related to whole-child development, teachers are more likely to integrate such principles into their teaching. In PLCs where the importance of non-academic skills is emphasized, teachers have the opportunity to refine their understanding of holistic education and incorporate it into their instructional practices (Nunez, et.al, 2023). Kindergarten teachers in Davao Oriental, like many educators globally, face a unique set of challenges when it comes to promoting whole-child development. One of the primary challenges is the limited availability of resources and support systems. In many cases, teachers struggle with overcrowded classrooms, limited teaching materials, and inadequate access to professional development opportunities. This resource constraint can hinder their ability to create a well-rounded educational environment

that caters to individual student needs. Additionally, cultural and societal expectations in the region may place a heavy emphasis on academic achievement, which can sometimes overshadow the importance of social-emotional and physical development. This presents a challenge for kindergarten teachers who wish to prioritize holistic education, as they may feel pressure to conform to more traditional, academic-centered approaches (Medina, 2022). Teacher workload and class sizes can be another hurdle. With large class sizes and extensive administrative demands, teachers may find it challenging to provide individualized attention to each child and address their unique developmental needs effectively. Lastly, limited access to training and professional development programs can hinder teachers' ability to keep up with evolving best practices and innovative approaches to whole-child development (Nunez, et.al., 2023). Overcoming these challenges requires a collaborative effort from educators, policymakers, and the community to provide the necessary support, resources, and recognition of the significance of holistic education in Davao Oriental's kindergarten classrooms. School administrators who emphasize a well-rounded approach to student growth have fostered a collective perception among educators that values the nurturing of not only academic skills but also social, emotional, physical, and moral development. Professional learning communities have provided a platform for kindergarten teachers in Davao Oriental to collaborate, share best practices, and access valuable professional development opportunities. Within these communities, teachers have engaged in reflective discussions, exchanged ideas related to whole-child development, and honed their teaching strategies accordingly. This collaborative culture has encouraged teachers to integrate principles of holistic education into their instructional practices.

2. Methodology

Research method refers to the systematic approach or strategy researchers use to conduct their investigations. It outlines how data is gathered, analyzed, and interpreted in a structured way to answer research questions and achieve research objectives. In essence, it's the plan or roadmap for carrying out a research study. In this context understanding the research method was essential for both researchers and readers as it determines the validity and reliability of the study's findings and contributes to the broader body of knowledge in the field of inquiry. This aims to elucidate the key components and considerations associated with the chosen research method, setting the stage for a comprehensive exploration of the research methodology employed in the study.

2.1. Research Design—The non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design was a comprehensive research approach that combined several vital elements. It was non-experimental, for it does not involve the manipulation of variables or establishing a cause-and-effect relationship. Instead, it focuses on observing and measuring existing phenomena as they naturally occur. Second, it was descriptive in nature, aiming to provide a detailed and systematic account of a particular subject or topic. This involves collecting data through surveys, observations, or existing records to describe and summarize the characteristics, behaviors, or conditions under investigation. Third, it was correlational, which means it seeks to identify relationships or associations between variables. This involves analyzing data to determine whether changes in one variable are related to changes in another without implying causation. Lastly, it was predictive, often aiming to make informed predictions or forecasts based on the identified correlations. By understanding the relationships between variables, researchers can use this knowledge to make reasonable predictions about future outcomes or trends (Creswel, 2014). The descriptive aspect allows researchers to paint a detailed picture of kindergarten teachers' perceptions. At the same time, the correlational component assists in identifying potential connections between the variables of interest leadership practices and professional learning communities. Through statistical analysis, researchers can determine whether a relationship exists, the direction of this relationship, and the strength of its association. The predictive element of the research design goes a step further by using the data collected to make informed predictions or inferences about how leadership practices and professional learning communities may impact kindergarten teachers' perceptions of whole-child development in the future. This provides valuable insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers on potential areas for improvement and intervention in early childhood education. In summary, the non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design offers a holistic and data-driven approach to understanding the complex interplay between leadership, professional learning communities, and kindergarten teachers' perceptions of whole-child development, which can ultimately inform strategies for enhancing the educational experience for young children.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were kindergarten teachers in the Gov Gen South District, Davao Oriental area. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, and 60 teacher-respondents were taken randomly from each school surrounding the area. After being selected through randomization, respondents were notified both online and in person, taking into account the availability of Wi-Fi connections. Additionally, they received an orientation regarding the study's objectives and its sig-

nificance in relation to their professional development. The selection of teacher-respondents was based on the assumption that they are actively involved in handling kindergarten learners. They were expected to have a strong engagement with the policies and programs in implementing the Early Childhood Development Program, as well as the day-to-day management and execution of various school-based learning programs, projects, and activities designed to enhance early learners' development within the framework of school-based management. The qualifications for participation in this study were rooted in the expectation that they had made significant contributions, extending beyond their primary roles in curriculum delivery, implementation, and governance, by actively participating in various educational activities. These contributions were typically discussed during school faculty meetings, group sessions, and committee meetings, all to improve the school environment and students' educational experiences during the new standard learning system in the academic year 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support of the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible contamination and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—The instrument employed in this research study was meticulously crafted through a comprehensive review

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The statements provide a clear overview of the sequential steps that define the data collection process. It was imperative that the researcher care-

fully consider and strictly follow these steps, adhering to the policies of Rizal Memorial Colleges and the guidelines set forth by the IATF. This approach is vital to ensure safety and mitigation of existing literature and related studies. The researcher dedicated substantial effort to gathering and analyzing relevant literature, extracting key concepts that not only guided the instrument's development but also fortified its alignment with the designated strands. This thorough procedure contributed to creating a well-structured set of questionnaire items, thereby bolstering the overall validity of the instrument and mitigating potential challenges to its reliability. Items were adapted from the reviewed literature, as the authors argued. The survey questionnaire had two parts, which consisted of indicators of leadership practices in terms of instructional leadership, decision-making authority, vision and goal setting, and teacher support; likewise, indicators of professional learning community in terms of collaboration, professional development opportunities, and trust and communication. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured kindergarten teachers' perceptions of whole-child development in terms of self-assessment of whole-child focus, attitude towards holistic teaching, perceived importance of non-academic skills, and beliefs about role-play. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a 0.05 confidence level. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.879, meaning there is an 87.9 percent confidence level in the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant, 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of leadership practices and professional learning community. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation were provided below:

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Descriptive Rating for Whole-Child Development

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The whole-child development is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The whole-child development is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The whole-child development is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The whole-child development is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The whole-child development is not manifested.

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gate any potential risks associated with gathering relevant data, especially given the current context of ongoing in-person interactions. Permission to conduct the study. In the second week of December 2023, the researcher initiated the process of conceptualizing the content and objectives of the thesis proposal. Subsequently, she prepared various documents, including request letters, for the study. The research study strictly adhered to established ethical data collection procedures, as Creswell (2004) outlined, and followed the health protocols. The research proposal was approved by the panel of members and the college dean in the last week of February to the first week of March 2024, the researcher composed and submitted a formal letter seeking permission to collect data and conduct the study within Gov Gen South District to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Oriental, following the proper channels. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In May 2024, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for

the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents without internet access. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with data gathering, which commenced on the third week of May 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of June 2024. For coaching and in terms of statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician to provide technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study sometime in the first week of June 2024 and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results on the second week of June 2024.

2.5. *Data Analysis—*

Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of leadership practices and professional learning communities, and statement problem number two (2) on the whole-child development. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between leadership practices and professional learning communities and whole-

child development. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of leadership practices and professional learning communities that significantly influence whole-child development (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations then followed when results yield.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the researcher addresses the collection of data and its subsequent presentation, analysis, and interpretation. Both tabular and textual formats are employed to enhance the depth of analysis and facilitate the extraction of meaningful implications. Additionally, these presentations serve as supporting evidence for the hypothesis put forth.

Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of leadership practices and professional learning communities. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: decision-making authority (3.46) and collaboration (3.45) are oftentimes manifested; while, vision and goal setting (3.37), instructional leadership (3.22), trust and communication (3.21), professional development opportunities (3.13) and teacher support (3.12) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.28 denotes the extent of leadership practices and professional learning communities is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. Zhang, Huang and Ye (2023) investigated the mediating effects of professional learning

community (PLC) components on the relationship between leadership practices and teacher collective efficacy from the perspective of Chinese principals. Survey data were collected from 878 school principals. The results revealed that leadership practices significantly and positively affected the five PLC components, three of which (shared purpose, collective focus on student learning and reflective dialogue) had significant positive effects on teacher collective efficacy. Shared purpose, collective focus on student learning and reflective dialogue significantly mediated the effects of leadership practices on teacher collective efficacy. The practical implications of the findings and suggestions for future research are discussed.

School principals and teachers are expected to continuously innovate their practices in changing school environments. These innovation processes can be shared more widely through collaboration between principals and teachers, i.e. "collaborative innovation." Based on 11 leadership practices, de Jong, et.al., (2022) described two main leadership patterns: school principals enacting leadership practices

as either a "team player" or as a "facilitator." They conclude that our findings suggest a wider repertoire of leadership practices than is reported in previous studies. Sultan et al. (2022) identify the correlation between the instructional leadership practices of headmasters and the level of performance and achievement of schools in Malaysia. Thus, the findings conclude that the level of instructional leader-

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Leadership Practices and Professional Learning Communities

Leadership Practices and Professional Learning Communities	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Instructional leadership	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Decision-making authority	3.46	Extensive
Vision and goal setting	3.37	Moderately Extensive
Teacher support	3.12	Moderately Extensive
Collaboration	3.45	Extensive
Professional development opportunities	3.13	Moderately Extensive
Trust and communication	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.28	Moderately Extensive

ship practices among headmasters in primary schools is high and has a weak negative relationship with schools’ achievement. Table 2 shows the summary of the extent of teachers’ perception of whole-child development. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: beliefs about role play (3.87), self-assessment of

whole-child focus (3.46) and perceived importance of non-acad skills (3.43) are oftentimes manifested; attitude towards holistic teaching (2.99) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.43 denotes the extent of kinder learner success is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of Teacher Perception of Whole-Child Development

Teachers’ Perception of Whole-Child Development	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Self-assessment of whole-child focus	3.46	Extensive
Attitude towards holistic teaching	2.99	Moderately Extensive
Perceived importance of non-academic skills	3.43	Extensive
Beliefs about role play	3.87	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.43	Extensive

A developmentally appropriate learning environment provides learning experiences that support whole child development as young children are provided with opportunities to engage in meaningful experiences that promote inquiry,

exploration, problem-solving, and discovery. The intent of developmentally appropriate practice (DAP) is shifting the K-12 pushdown curriculum in early childhood education (ECE) to a child-centered approach to learning. Qualifi-

cation in fields unrelated to ECE might result in a lack of knowledge about child growth and development and in childcare centers functioning like K-12 programs. Findings suggest that a disturbing amount of toddler and preschool teachers endorsed a K-12 pushdown curriculum with the belief that young children should be able to sit and complete worksheets (Cade et.al., 2022). Keung et.al. (2020) examined the relationships between leadership practices, professional learning communities, teachers' efficacy beliefs, and perceptions of whole-child development in the context of kindergarten education. The results showed that principals' leadership practices had significant effects on all five professional learning community components. Leadership practices were also positively related to teachers' perceptions of whole-child development directly and indirectly through the mediation of three professional learning community components, namely a shared sense of purpose, collaborative activities and a collective focus on children's learning. Moreover, three professional learning community components (i.e. a collective focus on children's learning, de-privatized practice and reflective dialogue) were positively associated with teachers' per-

ceptions of whole-child development via their efficacy beliefs. The findings support the mediating role of professional learning communities in developing kindergarten teachers' collaboration to improve their efficacy beliefs and perceptions of the whole-child development of children. Kindergarten principals play a key role in cultivating a supportive culture and facilitating teacher learning. Relationship between Leadership Practices and Professional Learning Communities and Perception of Whole-Child Development

It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between leadership practices and professional learning communities ($r=0.895$; $p<.001$) and perception of whole-child development. Table 3 revealed the yielded results of the significant relationship between leadership practices and professional learning communities and perception of whole-child development. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis, stating that there is no significant relationship between leadership practices and professional learning communities and perception of whole-child development, must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence to show its correlation.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Leadership Practices and Professional Learning Communities and Perception of Whole-Child Development

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Perception of Whole-Child Development	0.895	<0.001	Significant	Reject H

**Significant at $p<0.05$.*

The significant relationship between leadership practices and professional learning communities (PLCs) plays a crucial role in shaping the perception of whole-child development within educational settings. Acar, et.al., (2021) said that effective leadership practices, such as

visionary guidance, collaboration, and instructional support, contribute to the establishment and sustenance of PLCs. These communities, comprised of educators working collaboratively to enhance teaching and learning, foster an environment that prioritizes holistic student devel-

opment. Leadership within PLCs encourages the exchange of ideas, best practices, and a collective commitment to addressing not only academic growth but also the socio-emotional and physical well-being of students. The synergy between leadership practices and PLCs amplifies the perception of whole-child development, emphasizing a comprehensive approach to education that considers not only academic achievement but also the social, emotional, and physical dimensions of a student's growth and well-being. Al-Khayat, et.al., (2023) explored the interplay between leadership practices and professional learning communities (PLCs) is foundational to creating a school culture that values and supports whole-child development. Leadership practices that involve setting a clear vision for the school, promoting collaboration among educators, and providing targeted instructional support create a conducive environment for the formation and effectiveness of PLCs. These communities act as collaborative forums where teachers share insights, strategies, and resources, fostering a collective commitment to addressing the diverse needs of students. In the context of whole-child development, Becker, et.al., (2023) examine the relationship between leadership and PLCs extends beyond academic growth. It encompasses the social, emotional, and physical dimensions of students' well-being. Leadership that promotes a holistic approach recognizes that education is not solely about achieving high test scores but also about nurturing well-rounded individuals. PLCs become instrumental in translating this vision into action by facilitating discussions on incorporating social-emotional learning into the curriculum, implementing inclusive practices, and addressing the physical health and safety of students. Moreover, Kula (2022) determine the collaboration within PLCs enhances educators' understanding of each student's unique strengths, challenges, and backgrounds. This personalized insight allows for targeted interventions and support sys-

tems that cater to the diverse needs of students. Leadership practices that prioritize whole-child development, coupled with the collaborative nature of PLCs, create a symbiotic relationship that goes beyond traditional academic metrics, embracing a comprehensive perspective on education. In this way, the synergy between leadership and PLCs contributes significantly to shaping a school culture that values and actively promotes the holistic development of every student. Domains of Leadership Practices and Professional Learning Communities Significantly Influence Perception of Whole-Child Development

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on domains of leadership practices and professional learning communities significantly influence perception of whole-child development. Domains of leadership practices and professional learning communities in terms of instructional leadership (0.001), teacher support (0.010), collaboration (0.002), trust and communication (0.000) and decision-making authority (0.000) significantly influenced whole-child development. Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.879 suggests that whole-child development, can be explained by 87.9 of leadership practices and professional learning communities. This provides empirical evidence that variability of whole-child development can be accounted and be explained by leadership practices and professional learning communities. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (254.588) and F-statistic is significant $p < .010$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of whole-child development. Leadership practices and professional learning communities (PLCs) wield a profound influence on the perception of whole-child development within educational contexts. Effective leadership practices, characterized by visionary guidance, collaboration, and a commitment to instructional support, set the tone for a

school culture that prioritizes the holistic growth of students. When these leadership qualities are coupled with the establishment and functioning of PLCs, the impact becomes even more pronounced (Cade, et.al., 2022). PLCs provide a structured platform for educators to collaboratively delve into pedagogical strategies, share insights, and collectively address the diverse needs of students. The collaborative nature of PLCs encourages discussions and initiatives that extend beyond traditional academic measures, emphasizing the social, emotional, and physical dimensions of students' well-being (Elliott, et.al., 2021).

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Leadership Practices and Professional Learning Communities Significantly Influence Perception of Whole-Child Development

Model	B	Beta	SE	Standard Error	SE	p-value	Decisions
H (Intercept)	4.145	0.079		60.416	0.001	4.143	
H (Intercept)	0.313	0.175		1.066	0.270	0.202	
	0.817	0.117	0.101	1.010	0.315	0.001	*Reject H
Instructional Leadership							
Teacher Support	0.431	0.118	0.132	1.279	0.196	0.010	*Reject H
Collaboration	0.212	0.097	0.211	2.088	0.038	0.002	*Reject H
Trust and Communication	0.921	0.508	0.136	1.269	0.296	0.000	*Reject H
Decision-making Authority	0.502	0.057	0.210	3.098	0.038	0.000	*Reject H
R ²	0.879						
F-value	254.588						
p-value	<0.010						

**Significant at p<0.05.*

This collaborative effort, guided by effective leadership, results in a shared understanding and commitment to whole-child development. Teachers within PLCs not only exchange best practices but also explore innovative ways to incorporate social-emotional learning, inclusivity, and physical health into the educational framework. In essence, the symbiotic relationship between leadership practices and PLCs significantly shapes the perception of whole-child development, fostering a comprehensive approach to education that goes beyond academic achievement to embrace the multifaceted aspects of students' growth and well-being (Weißrieder, et.al., 2015). Acar, et.al., (2021) examined the relationship between leadership practices and professional learning communities (PLCs) has a synergistic impact on how educators perceive and approach whole-child development. Leadership practices, including visionary guidance, collaboration, and instructional support, create a school culture that recognizes the importance of nurturing every aspect of a student's growth. These practices set the stage for the establish-

ment of PLCs, which serve as collaborative forums where teachers collectively engage in ongoing professional development and learning. Within PLCs, educators share their experiences, insights, and best practices, creating a dynamic exchange that transcends traditional academic concerns. The collaborative nature of PLCs allows educators to delve into discussions on how to incorporate social-emotional learning into the curriculum, promote inclusivity, and address the physical well-being of students (Hallam, et.al., 2015). Effective leadership ensures that these discussions are not mere theoretical exercises but translate into actionable strategies integrated into the daily educational practices. As a result, the partnership between leadership practices and PLCs influences the perception of whole-child development by fostering a holistic approach to education. This approach recognizes that students are not only learners of academic content but indi-

viduals with unique social, emotional, and physical needs. Teachers within PLCs gain a deeper understanding of their students' diverse backgrounds and challenges, enabling them to tailor their instructional methods and support systems accordingly (Kelly, et.al., 2022). In essence, the collaboration between leadership and PLCs creates a transformative environment where the entire educational community is aligned toward a shared commitment to whole-child development. This comprehensive perspective extends beyond traditional metrics of success, emphasizing the importance of cultivating well-rounded individuals who are academically proficient, socially and emotionally resilient, and physically healthy. The dynamic interplay between leadership practices and PLCs thus becomes a cornerstone in shaping a positive and holistic educational experience for students (Morrissey and Kenny, 2023).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analysis, discussion, and drawing of implications. Findings were based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions were based on the findings generated and recommendations were based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following were the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The leadership practices and professional learning communities in terms of decision-making authority (3.46) and collaboration (3.45) are extensive while vision and goal setting (3.37), instructional leadership (3.22), trust and communication (3.21), professional development opportunities (3.13) and teacher support (3.12) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.28 denotes that leadership practices and professional learning communities is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The teachers' perception of whole-child de-

velopment in terms of beliefs about role play (3.87), self-assessment of whole-child focus (3.46) and perceived importance of non-acad skills (3.43) are oftentimes manifested; attitude towards holistic teaching (2.99) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.43 denotes that kinder learner success is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant relationship between leadership practices and professional learning communities ($r=0.895$; $p<.001$) and perception of whole-child development. Domains of leadership practices and professional learning communities in terms of instructional leadership (0.001), teacher support (0.010), collaboration

(0.002), trust and communication (0.000), and decision-making authority (0.000) significantly influenced whole-child development.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Given the findings of the study presented, the following were conclusions to wit; The leadership practices and professional learning communities in terms of decision-making authority and collaboration are oftentimes manifested; while, vision and goal setting, instructional leadership, trust and communication, professional development opportunities and teacher support were sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of whole-child development in terms of beliefs about role play, self-assessment of whole-child focus and perceived importance of non-academic skills are oftentimes manifested; attitude towards holistic teaching is sometimes manifested, thus, extensive. There was a significant relationship between leadership practices, professional learning communities and perception of whole-child development. Domains of leadership practices and professional learning communities in terms of instructional leadership, teacher support, collaboration, trust, communication, and decision-making authority significantly influence whole-child development.

4.3. *Recommendations*—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following were recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. It may encourage and support professional development programs for school leaders that focus on effective leadership practices, emphasizing the importance of visionary guidance, collaboration, and instructional support. Foster the establishment and maintenance of robust professional learning communities within schools, providing resources and guidance to ensure their effectiveness. Advocate for a holistic approach to education at the

district level, promoting policies that recognize and prioritize the social, emotional, and physical dimensions of whole-child development. School Principal. May implement leadership practices that prioritize the comprehensive development of students, ensuring a clear vision, collaborative ethos, and adequate instructional support. Facilitate the formation and sustenance of professional learning communities within the school, providing time and resources for educators to collaborate and share best practices. Integrate whole-child development principles into the school's curriculum, policies, and practices, fostering an environment that nurtures students' academic, social, emotional, and physical well-being. Teacher. May Actively participate in and contribute to professional learning communities, sharing insights, experiences, and innovative practices that enhance the holistic development of students. Embrace and implement whole-child development strategies within their classrooms, recognizing the importance of addressing social, emotional, and physical aspects alongside academic growth. Continuously engage in professional development opportunities to enhance their understanding of effective teaching methods that cater to the diverse needs of students. Future Researcher. May Explore further the nuanced dynamics between specific leadership practices and their impact on different aspects of whole-child development within diverse educational contexts. Investigate the long-term effects of sustained professional learning communities on both teacher effectiveness and student outcomes, considering variations in school size, demographics, and geographic location. Delve into the potential role of vision and goal setting, and professional development opportunities, keeping in mind the evolving nature of education.

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